

ANNEX-I

Developing Integrated PBPK/PD Coupled mechanistic pathway model (miRNA-BDNF): an approach towards System toxicology

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Model equations for PBPK/PD coupled mechanistic model

%#Model equations for PFOS

$$\frac{d}{dt}(A_{gut}) = Q_{gut} * \left(c_{plasma} * fu - c_{gut} * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{gut_{plasma}}} \right) \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(A_{liver}) = Q_{liver} * c_{plasma} * fu + Q_{gut} * c_{gut} * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{gut_{plasma}}} \right) - \left((Q_{liver} + Q_{gut}) * c_{liver} * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{liver_{plasma}}} \right) \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(A_{brain}) = Q_{brain} * \left(c_{plasma} * fu - c_{brain} * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{brain_{plasma}}} \right) \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(A_{fat}) = Q_{fat} * \left(c_{plasma} * fu - c_{fat} * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{fat_{plasma}}} \right) \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(A_{kidney}) = Q_{kidney} * \left(c_{plasma} * fu - c_{kidney} * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{kidney_{plasma}}} \right) \right) + \left(\frac{Tm * c_{filterate}}{kt + c_{filterate}} \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(A_{filterate}) = Q_{filterate} * (c_{plasma} * fu - c_{filterate}) - \left(\frac{Tm * c_{filterate}}{kt + c_{filterate}} \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(Adelay) = Qfilterate * cfilterate - kurine * Adelay$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(Alung) = Qlung * \left(cplasma * fu - clung * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{lung_plasma}} \right) \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(Abm) = Qbm * \left(cplasma * fu - cbm * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{bm_plasma}} \right) \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(Arestbody) = Qrestbody * \left(cplasma * fu - crestbody * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{restbody_plasma}} \right) \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(Aurine) = Kurine * Adelay$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(Aplasma) = Qfat * cfat * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{fat_plasma}} \right) + (Qliver + Qgut) * cliver * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{liver_plasma}} \right) + \left(Qbrain * cbrain * \left(\frac{fu}{k_{brain_plasma}} \right) \right) + Qlu$$

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Mechanistic base Model equations

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$$\frac{d}{dt}(pri_{miRNA}) = k1 - k2 * pri_{miRNA} - k * R - d1 * pri_{miRNA}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(pre_{miRNA_n}) = k2 * pri_{miRNA} + k * R - d2 * pre_{miRNA_n} - k3 * pre_{miRNA_n} * \left(\frac{vp}{vn} \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(pre_{miRNA_c}) = \left(\frac{vp}{vn} \right) * k3 * pre_{miRNA_n} - d3 * pre_{miRNA_c} - k4 * pre_{miRNA_c}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(dsRNA) = k4 * pre_{miRNA_c} - d4 * dsRNA - k5 * dsRNA$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(miRNA) = k5 * dsRNA + k11 * RISC - d5 * miRNA - k6 * miRNA$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(mRNA) = km + k_8 * RISCm - k_7 * RISC * mRNA - d_8 * mRNA$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(RISC) = k_9 * RISCm + k_8 * RISCm + k_6 * miRNA - d_6 * RISC - k_7 * RISC * mRNA - k_{11} * RISC$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(RISCm) = k_7 * RISC * mRNA - k_9 * RISCm - k_8 * RISCm - d_7 * RISCm$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(BDNF) = k_{10} * mRNA - d_9 * BDNF$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(cellsurvivability) = d_9 * BDNF * \left(1 + \left(\frac{Emax_{cell} * BDNF}{EC50_{BDNF} + BDNF} \right) \right) - k_{d_{cell}} * cell$$

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PBPK/PD Model coupled mechanistic signalling pathway Model

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$$\frac{d}{dt}(pri_{miRNA_{change}}) = k_1 - k_2 * pri_{miRNA_{change}} - k * R - d_1 * pri_{miRNA_{change}}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(pre_{miRNA_{change}}) = k_2 * pri_{miRNA_{change}} + k * R - d_2 * pre_{miRNA_{change}} - k_3 * pre_{miRNA_{change}} * \left(\frac{vp}{vn} \right)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(pre_{miRNA_{change}}) = \left(\frac{vp}{vn} \right) * k_3 * pri_{miRNA_{change}} - d_3 * pre_{miRNA_{change}} - k_4 * pre_{miRNA_{change}}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(dsRNA_{change}) = k_4 * pre_{miRNA_{change}} - d_4 * dsRNA_{change} - k_5 * dsRNA_{change}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(miRNA_{change}) = k_5 * dsRNA * \left(1 + \left(\frac{Emax_{miRNA} * cbrain}{EC50_{miRNA} + cbrain} \right) \right) + k_{11} * RISC_{change} - d_5 * miRNA_{change} - k_6 * miRNA_{change}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(mRNA_{change}) = km + k_8 * RISCm_{change} - k_7 * RISC_{change} * mRNA_{change} - d_8 * mRNA_{change}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(RISC_{change}) = k_9 * RISC_{m_{change}} + k_8 * RISC_{m_{change}} + k_6 * miRNA_{A_{change}} - d_6 * RISC_{change} - k_7 * RISC_{change}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(RISC_{m_{change}}) = k_7 * RISC_{change} * miRNA_{A_{change}} - k_9 * RISC_{m_{change}} - k_8 * RISC_{m_{change}} - d_7 * RISC_{m_{change}}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(BDNF_{change}) = k_{10} * miRNA_{A_{change}} - d_9 * BDNF_{change}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(cell\ survivability_{change}) = d_9 * BDNF_{change} * \left(1 + \left(\frac{Emax_{cell} * BDNF_{change}}{EC50_{BDNF} + BDNF_{change}} \right) \right) - k_{d_{cell}} * cell_{change}$$

Table 1. Physiological parameters used for PBPK model

QCC = 20	Cardiac blood output (L/h/kg^{0.75})
FQliver = 0.25	Fraction cardiac output going to liver
FQbrain = 0.117	Fraction cardiac output going to brain
FQkidney = 0.177	Fraction cardiac output going to kidney
FQfilterate = 0.035	Fraction cardiac output to the filtrate compartment
FQgut = 0.181	Fraction cardiac output going to gut
FQbm = 0.1	Fraction cardiac output going to bone marrow
FQfat = 0.052	Fraction cardiac output going to fat
FQlung = 0.034	Fraction cardiac output going to lung
Fraction tissue volume of BW	
Fliver = 0.026	Fraction liver volume
Fbrain = 0.021	Fraction brain volume
Fkidney = 0.004	Fraction kidney volume
Ffilterate = 0.0004	Fraction filtrate compartment volume
Ffat = 0.187	Fraction fat compartment volume
Flung = 0.014	Fraction of lung volume
Fbm = 0.05	Fraction bone marrow volume
Fplasma = 0.0428	fraction volume of plasma
Fgut = 0.0171	Fraction gut

Table 2. Physicochemical parameter For PFOS

fu = 0.025	Free fraction of PFOS in plasma
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k_liver_plasma = 2.2	Liver/blood partition coefficient
k_gut_plasma = 0.05	Gut/blood partition coefficient
k_brain_plasma = 0.37	brain/blood partition coefficient
k_kidney_plasma = 1.05	Kidney/blood partition coefficient
k_fat_plasma = 0.04	Fat/blood partition coefficient
k_lung_plasma = 9.08	Skin/blood partition coefficient
k_bm_plasma = 18.73	bone marrow/blood partition coefficient
k_restbody_plasma = 0.120	Rest of the body/blood partition coefficient
Tmc = 7.0	resorption maximum (nmole/h/kg ^{0.75}); from adult human model
kt = 0.023	affinity constant; from monkey model
kurinec = 0.1	urinary elimination rate constant (1/h)
kurine = kurinec*BW**(-0.25)	urine elimination
Tm = Tmc*BW**0.75	transporter maximum (scaled as BW ^{0.75})
